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Optimizing Coastal Energy Generation: Scheduling an Isolated Microgrid with a Co-located Wind-wave Farm and Storage

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Abstract

Interest in using marine energy in microgrids for powering coastal or islanded communities has grown. A challenge for such an approach while avoiding conventional diesel generators is the variability of offshore energy resources (offshore wind, wave, tidal, etc.) for power production. Energy storage technologies are commonly used to mitigate variability; however, they are expensive. Ensuring that an isolated (i.e., disconnected from the electric grid) microgrid has enough power to meet the demand requires an accurate assessment of supply-demand matching using site-specific resource data and modeling of co-located wind-wave farms. This study formulates optimal resource allocation, also known as the economic dispatch problem of an islanded microgrid for coastal communities, by integrating a battery energy storage system with offshore wind turbines, wave energy converters, and solar photovoltaic generation. The economic dispatch problem was formulated as a constrained linear programming problem to minimize the hourly costs of operating different resources. The results of these studies show that the implementation of offshore renewable energy technologies for islanded communities requires large storage systems unless the generating devices produce much more average power than is needed. Also, using a mix of different renewable energy systems yields reductions in cost and storage size when compared to using a single type of device.

Keywords: isolated microgrid; WEC; economic dispatch; battery energy storage

1. Introduction

Integrating renewable resources into microgrids is made difficult by their high level of variability relative to conventional diesel generators. The use of advanced scheduling optimization techniques and energy storage technologies can allow for renewable integration, and previous research has already addressed this for onshore wind and solar. Li et al. [1] integrated wind turbines, photovoltaic (PV) energy, microturbines, and energy storage technologies into a microgrid. They used a bi-level problem formulation that included both users and operators as stakeholders and led to operator revenue increases of 10% and user cost decreases of 6%. Although the probabilistic resource models used by Li et al. encapsulate some uncertainty in resource availability, they may not capture the exact resource distribution for a real site. A work that used real wind data is by Sun et al. [2], who used a support vector machine method to forecast wind speeds with uncertainty. The authors then showed that their wind forecasting method can produce good results and confidence intervals. Neither author considered offshore wind turbines or wave energy converters in their works. It is well known that offshore wind has better availability and lower variability than onshore wind, as well as higher wind speeds [3]. Neither author included a variable BESS cost in their dispatch models.

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Although the integration of onshore wind and solar energy into microgrids has been examined, the integration of co-located wind and wave energy into isolated microgrids has not been explored as much. The advantages of co-located farms from an economic standpoint have been discussed in the literature. Clark et al. [4] made use of possible savings for such a farm by considering the pre-installation, implementation, operation, and decommissioning costs of wind-wave farms. They then calculated the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) in a case study for a location in the North Sea and found that co-located offshore wind and wave farms can potentially have three-fourths to half the cost of a pure offshore wind farm. However, in their modeling of the farm LCOE, they did schedule the farm output for any demand. Kluger et al. [5] implemented an isolated grid-level offshore wind-wave farm with onshore compressed air storage and a gas turbine. They considered historical data for a coastal site in California and optimized the storage schedule. They found that a combined wind-wave farm provided smoother and less variable power. Kluger et al. did not discuss the economic benefits of a co-located wind-wave farm. In the present work, we aim to use site-specific data and a variable BESS cost to demonstrate the economic effects of integrating co-located wind-wave energy converters into islanded microgrids.

2. Methods and Modeling

Scheduling an isolated microgrid with offshore energy and storage systems requires accurate accounts of the available resources to meet demand. In this work, the schedule optimization is evaluated on an hourly basis, so accurate modeling of available system power is needed by the hour. The microgrid system considered for this study consists of up to two OWTs and up to two farms of six wave energy converters (WECs). In addition, a farm of PV cells, as well as a battery energy storage system (BESS), is considered.

Figure 1. (left) Locations of interest for this study (hourly wind and wave data were obtained from NOAA buoys); (right) Sea state matrix showing bins of wave height and wave period and the number of occurrences of that sea state in 2020 for buoy 41056 (PR)

2.1. Site-specific Data Resources & Energy Convertors

The microgrid is optimized for three sites on the U.S. Atlantic Coast in Puerto Rico (PR), Florida (FL), and New York City (NY), (see Figure 1 (left)); all locations have hourly wind and wave data [6] available. The site in PR is chosen because it is an island with shallow waters nearby and represents a possible set of ocean conditions for an islanded community. The choice of the other two sites is to provide a comparison and verification of the first site. The wind speeds are recorded at 4 m above the mean sea level. The turbine has a hub height of 44 m above sea level, so a log wind profile with a roughness factor ($z_0 = 0.0002$ m) based on open sea conditions is used to interpolate the wind speed at the turbine hub height. Data for the PV farm is obtained from the National Solar Radiation Database [7], while the demand data is taken from the National Energy Information Administration [8]. To generate the load profiles for the microgrids at PR and FL, demand data from the state of Florida is used, while the NY load profile is obtained from New York City data.

The OWT modeled in this study is an AOC 15/50 turbine model [9] (50 kW rated output at a rated speed of 11.3 m/s). The OWT unit is mounted on a single monopile and is modeled using openFAST [10]. The wind speeds from the buoy data are binned into 0.5 m/s intervals and the average turbine power is then calculated for each bin. To extract energy from ocean waves, a total of six WECs (two-body floating heave type with a rated output of 15 kW) are used

for this study. The WECs are placed in a farm around the OWT and modeled using Ansys AQWA in the frequency domain. The hydrodynamic data is then transferred to WEC-sim [11] to evaluate the farm performance in the time domain. The dominant wave heights and periods are binned into a sea state matrix (see Figure 1 (right) using a relevant wave spectrum (TMA: Texel Marsen Arsloe) for irregular waves in shallow waters (20-30 m depth) [12]. The PV power output is calculated using an assumption of maximum power point tracking for the PV cells; details of maximum power efficiency can be found in [13].

2.2. Economic Dispatch Problem

The levelized cost of energy is adopted from literature to represent the economic costs of each resource (offshore wind, wave, and solar) and a tradeoff in the dispatch model [14,15]. The cost coefficients used for this study are $k_{wind} = 0.1$ \$/kW-hr, $k_{PV} = 0.2$ \$/kW-hr, and $k_{WEC} = 0.3$ \$/kW-hr [14,15]. The BESS LCOE, k_{batt} is a function of the BESS size [16], with the dispatch being a constrained optimization problem where the system cost is minimized subject to the constraints of available power, energy in storage, and a power balance with demand. Maximum and minimum power outputs for the resources are given as constraints to the problem. For a given hour, the optimization is formulated in equation (1) a-i.

$$\text{minimize}(k_{wind}P_{wind} + k_{PV}P_{PV} + k_{WEC}P_{WEC} + k_{batt}P_{batt}H(P_{batt})) \quad (1a)$$

$$\text{subject to } P_{wind} + P_{PV} + P_{WEC} + P_{batt} = P_{demand} \quad (1b)$$

$$0 \leq P_{wind} \leq P_{wind,max} \quad (1c)$$

$$0 \leq P_{PV} \leq P_{PV,max} \quad (1d)$$

$$0 \leq P_{WEC} \leq P_{WEC,max} \quad (1e)$$

$$-200 \leq P_{batt} \leq 200 \quad (1f)$$

$$E_{batt}(t) = E_{batt}(t-1) - P_{batt}(t) \quad (1g)$$

$$\text{if } P_{wind} + P_{PV} + P_{WEC} \leq P_{demand}, \text{ then: } 0 \leq E_{batt}(t) \leq E_{batt,max} \quad (1h)$$

$$\text{elseif } P_{wind} + P_{PV} + P_{WEC} \geq P_{demand}, \text{ then: } \varepsilon E_{batt,max} \leq E_{batt}(t) \leq E_{batt,max} \quad (1i)$$

The symbols $P_{wind}, P_{PV}, P_{WEC}, P_{batt}, P_{demand}$ represent the power scheduled by the optimization for the wind turbine(s), solar farm, WEC(s), BESS, and the demand for the next hour. The inclusion of the word ‘‘max’’ in the subscript of these symbols indicates the total power those resources are generating in the next hour. The symbols $E_{batt}(t)$ and $E_{batt}(t-1)$ represent the energy in the storage system at the end of the next hour and the energy of the storage system at the end of the last hour. The notation ‘‘(t)’’ is left off the other variables for brevity, but all other powers are for the current hour. The symbol ε represents a fraction between 0 and 1, referred to as the charging aggression, which dictates how much energy the optimization will try to keep in the storage system whenever it has excess power. The symbol $H(P_{batt})$ indicates the Heaviside function of the battery power. Hence, the battery only has a cost associated with its usage and not with its charging. To find the value of $E_{batt,max}$ for a given configuration and season, this value is iterated until the smallest storage size that meets demand at all hours during the season is found.

3. Results

The microgrid scheduling is calculated for four different seasons with different configurations of OWTs, WECs, and PV farms that include up to 2 OWTs, 6 or 12 WECs, and up to 100 square meters of floating PV cells. The configuration of wind turbines and WECs in this work are abbreviated by the convention xTyW, where x represents the number of turbines, and y represents the number of 6-WEC farms considered.

3.1. Battery Energy Storage System Charging Strategy

Since the microgrid scheduling is carried out hourly, the choice of when to charge the BESS from the excess energy is unclear. Three values of charging aggression $\varepsilon = 0.3, 0.6, 0.9$ are chosen. Figure 2 shows the effect of varying charging aggression on the storage size and cost of the system for PR. It can be seen in Figure 2 (left) that the storage size of the 1T0W and 2T0W systems stays constant at 20MWhr and 15MWhr for different ε . Similar trends are seen for other configurations in Figure 2 (right) during spring. However, the configuration 1T1W in Figure 2 (left) varies with ε . For a charging aggression of 30%, the storage size is 6MWhr, but it is 3MWhr for a charging aggression of

Figure 2. (left) The minimum BESS capacity required; (right) The average cost of energy for the system

0.9. In Figure 2 (right), during fall, the cost of the 1T1W configuration decreases from 1.8 \$/kW-hr to 1 \$/kW-hr for the same change in ϵ . In the summer, the 2T0W system shows a different trend. The storage size moves from 10MWhr to 6MWhr to 15MWhr as the charging aggression increases from 0.3 to 0.6 to 0.9. Similarly, the cost changes from 2.5 \$/kW-hr to 1.8 \$/kW-hr and then to 4 \$/kW-hr. Although there is a local minimum in the 2T0W system in summer, most configuration costs either consistently decrease with charging aggression or are unaffected by it.

3.2. Effect of Variable Storage Levelized Cost of Energy

By including the BESS capacity in the calculation of k_{batt} , the optimization is significantly biased against larger BESS systems. To demonstrate this, Figure 3 (left) shows the average cost of energy for the NY site with the assumption that the BESS has an LCOE of 0.5 \$/kW-hr, regardless of its size. The costs remain below 0.5 \$/kW-hr, decreasing with solar integration. Additionally, higher power generation from wind-wave farms tends to correspond with reduced costs. However, in Figure 3 (left), the cost of the 2T0W system without solar is 0.34 \$/kW-hr, whereas the 1T1W farm – which produces more energy -- is more expensive at 0.37\$/kW-hr. Thus, more powerful farms are not always cheaper.

Compare these graphs to Figure 3 (right), in which the costs are much higher. Increased energy integration consistently leads to cost reduction. Where the 2T0W system costs 0.34 \$/kW-hr and the 1T1W system costs 0.37\$/kW-hr in Figure 3 (left), the 2T0W system costs 13.5 \$/kW-hr, and the 1T1W system costs 1.3 \$/kW-hr in Figure 3 (right). Despite the 1T1W system generating around 11 kW more on average in summer, it costs less due to lowered BESS size. This decrease in size, driven by added energy, leads to a larger cost reduction compared to the constant k_{batt} scenario.

Figure 3. (left) Average COE in NY with fixed storage cost; (right) Average COE in NY with variable storage cost

4. Conclusions

The optimal scheduling of a coastal microgrid with a BESS that is connected to offshore wind, wave, and solar energy converters is explored. Several configurations, storage sizes, and system economics are studied. The principal findings can be summarized as follows: Charging the BESS as much as possible to 90% of the maximum BESS capacity results in less required storage size and cost in many configurations such as the 1T1W configuration in winter and fall or the 1T2W system in spring and summer. There is an optimal charging aggression of 60% maximum battery that produces the lowest required size and cost during the summer in PR. The inclusion of BESS cost as a function of the BESS size has a significant impact on the cost of the microgrid. If the BESS cost is dependent on its size, then in the same conditions the 1T1W system costs approximately ten times less than the 2T0W system. Combining OWTs and WECs into a single system shows clear benefits to the required storage size and cost of the system. The combined wind-wave farms show a reduced cost of 50% in winter, 30% in spring, 30% in summer, and 3% in fall over either a pure wind or pure wave farm. This cost reduction is present even when the storage size of the wind-wave farm was not lessened.

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